

**GEOGRAPHICAL SERIES FOR ANALYSIS OF URBAN SOLID
WASTE IN BRAZIL**

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1 Introduction

This article presents a sample analysis of the year 2019 of Urban Solid Waste (MSW) management in Brazil. The original research that gave rise to this article was carried out using the National Information System on Solid Waste Management (Sinir) as a basis and for data mining also the SNIS - National Information System on Sanitation, 2020, with the support of the **R tool** * .

Severe negative impacts due to inadequate MSW such as contaminated water and soil and greenhouse gas emissions affect natural ecosystems, human health and social and economic activities in this region of the planet. It is estimated that around 145,000 tons per day of MSW are still discarded in landfills, burned or otherwise inappropriately disposed of (BIJOS, 2022).

The National Sanitation Information System (SNIS) was conceived by the Sanitation Sector Modernization Program (PMSS) and after its closure in February 2010, it has been developed and managed by the National Secretariat for Environmental Sanitation of the Ministry of Cities.

The SNIS relies on a database managed by the Ministry of Cities, which contains operational, managerial, financial and quality information on the provision of water and sewage services and on urban solid waste management services. .

In the case of water and sewage services, data are updated annually for a sample of service providers in Brazil, starting from the base year 1995. With regard to solid waste management services, data are also updated annually for a sample of Brazilian municipalities, since the base year of 2002.

The National Solid Waste Policy (PNRS) has as one of its objectives the observance of the following order of priority: “No generation, reduction, reuse, recycling and treatment of solid waste, as well as the environmentally appropriate final disposal of waste” (Brazil , 2010a)

The SNIS has established itself as the largest and most important database in the Brazilian sanitation sector, serving multiple purposes at the federal, state and municipal levels, among which the following stand out: (i) planning and execution of public policies; (ii) guidance on the application of resources; (iii) service performance evaluation; (iv) improvement of management, raising levels of efficiency and effectiveness; (v) orientation of regulatory and inspection activities; (vi) contribution to social control; and (vii) use of its indicators as a reference for comparison and for measuring performance in the Brazilian sanitation sector.

The historical series of SNIS data makes it possible to identify trends in relation to costs, revenues and service standards, to draw up inferences regarding the trajectory of the most

important variables for the sector, and thus, to design intervention strategies with greater basement. In addition, information and indicators in a historical perspective clarify myths and reveal realities about the provision of services to Brazilian society. This means opening up yet another space for society to act in demanding better services, through technical arguments and with a more consistent basis.

For the dissemination of its data, the SNIS annually publishes the Diagnosis of Water and Sewage Services and the Diagnosis of Solid Waste Management. It also has a website and an Application for the Historical Data Series, released on CD-ROM and also available on the Internet.

1.1 Question Problem

In today's world, it is necessary to consider the influences and interferences of a political, technical and cultural nature, resulting from the hegemonic capitalist model and the growing process of globalization that contribute to make the management of urban solid waste even more problematic.

This article is based on the research problem: at what level does the National Solid Waste Program influence the generation and collection of urban solid waste in Brazil?

1.2 Objectives

1.2.1 General Purpose

The article focuses on waste management, environmental impacts, life cycle, recycling and reverse logistics, analyzing Urban Solid Waste Management in Brazil.

1.2.2 Specific Objectives

- Analyze waste generation through the SINIR 2019 platform;
- Analyze the standard distribution of waste generation through the SINIS platform. 2020
- Compare the percentage sampling of residues in the macro-regions of Brazil by SINIR AND SINIS.

1.3 Justification

In 2010, the National Solid Waste Policy was instituted, imposing obligations on businessmen, governments and also on society as a whole so that waste could be managed. From this framework adjustments could be made, among them the problem found of government participation in several different groups and isolated projects. (AZEVEDO; SCAVARDA; GOYANNES, 2019)

Waste management can be analyzed from its aspects: the first one as a search of the State in the construction of programs; the second as a partnership between private institutions and the government for such management to take place (APPEL et al., 2020).

Therefore, the article is justified in seeking to analyze a geographic series of solid waste in Brazil.

2 Theoretical Basis

2.1 The National Solid Waste Policy

Federal Decree No. 7,404/2010 determines that the selective collection system will be implemented by the holder of the public urban cleaning and solid waste management service, that is, the municipalities themselves, and must establish, at a minimum, the separation of waste dry and wet, according to goals established in their respective plans (BRASIL, 2010b).

Source separation and selective collection are major bottlenecks for the efficiency of a waste management system, without which the possibility of recycling both inorganic and organic waste is significantly reduced.

The PNRS indicates in its article 45, however, that “the public consortia constituted, under the terms of Law nº 11.107, of 2005, aiming to make feasible the decentralization and provision of public services involving solid waste, have priority in obtaining the incentives instituted by the Federal Government” (Brasil, 2010a), which can be a great opportunity to overcome the financial, logistical and technical difficulties associated with most waste management operations in municipalities.

The National Solid Waste Plan (Planares), established by Decree No. 11,043, of April 13, 2022, is an important instrument of the National Solid Waste Policy as it presents a way to achieve the objectives and materialize the National Solid Waste Policy. Solid Waste through guidelines, strategies, actions and goals to improve solid waste management in the country. In

addition to the closure of all landfills, it is expected that waste recovery will increase to around 50% in 20 years. Thus, half of the waste generated will no longer be landfilled and will be reused through recycling, composting, biodigestion and energy recovery. Currently, only 2.2% of urban solid waste is recycled.

This new legislation offers legal security for the formation of consortia capable of managing public sanitation services, especially important for solid waste management, complying with the new requirements created by the Basic Sanitation Law and the National Solid Waste Policy. These requirements can be more easily implemented through the associated management of services, and aim to universalize the provision of services in the shortest possible time, with the best quality of services, and technical, economic, financial, environmental and social viability (BRASIL, 2010c, p.1).

The plan also provides for an increase in the recycling of civil construction waste to 25%, encourages the recycling of materials, contributes to the creation of green jobs, as well as enables better compliance with international commitments and multilateral agreements, and represents an important step in the process of Brazil's OECD membership. Waste recovery also reduces energy consumption and lower greenhouse gas emissions.

To prepare the Planares, a public consultation was held for more than one hundred days and six public hearings – one in each region of Brazil and a national public hearing. The document has a 20-year horizon, contributing to more legal certainty and predictability, essential for attracting investments.

2.2 Solid Waste Management in Brazil

Although there is a strong tendency to adopt, in Brazil and in peripheral countries, a solid waste management model, similar to that of developed countries, the general situation of this management is currently quite different from that found in the United States, Japan and India. European Union.

Globalization contributes considerably to the increase in the amount of solid waste, especially due to the consumption pattern disclosed by the media. In the perspective of globalization, the consumption-oriented lifestyle and the excessive use of packaging, continuously transferred as a model of behavior from developed to developing countries, are one of the main causes for the generation of waste and the growing increase in challenges to find sustainable solutions to the problems of urban solid waste (VALLINI, 2009)

The precariousness of urban cleaning systems in most Brazilian municipalities can be identified in the light of available data and information, despite the poor quality of many of them. It is understood that the axis of the urban cleaning system is in the structuring of household collection, in the cleaning of public places and in the proper destination of the collected residues.

In Brazil, the expansion of home collection and proper disposal of waste are still steps to be overcome; the production of urban solid waste is increasing and the standards achieved by recycling are not very significant in the set of the total generated. Recycling was implemented as an end in itself; adopting this process without a broad solid waste management program, mainly due to the bias that “recycling plants” could replace final disposal methods (Eigenheer et al. 2005).

3 Material and Methods

3.1 SINIR Indicators

The methodology seeks to present the analyzed data of solid waste in the geographic series in the macro regions of Brazil using information from SINIR, 2019. The data analyzed by the **R* platform** found inconsistencies, since, despite a national solid waste plan there is no effective municipal, state and regional control. Despite the existence of a National Waste Plan, it shows an array of problems, with provision in its National regularity.

3.1.1 Results

A typical solid waste management system in developing countries shows an array of problems.

3.2 Urban Solid Waste

Waste from domestic activities in urban residences (household waste) and waste originating from sweeping, cleaning public areas and roads and other urban cleaning services (urban cleaning waste).

- States declaring on **SINIR**
23 85.19%
- Declaring municipalities in **SINIR**
1,515 27.20%
- Declaring municipalities in the **SNIS**
3,712 66.64%

3.3 Types of Destination Adopted for RSU and Macroregions

Table 1 - Types of destination adopted for MSW (2019 Database)

Tipo de destinação	Massa (t)	%
Reciclagem	1.613.786,60	2,99
Compostagem	304.632,30	0,56
Unidade de manejo de galhadas e podas	142.625,10	0,26
Aterro sanitário	39.859.929,20	73,76
Aterro controlado	5.944.139,30	11,00
Lixão	6.177.442,00	11,43
Totais	54.042.554,50	100

Source: SINIR, 2019

Table 2 - Number of declarants by macro-region ((Database 2019)

Macrorregião	SINIR		SNIS
	Estados	Municípios	Municípios
Norte	4 (57,14%)	92 (20,44%)	239 (53,11%)
Nordeste	8 (88,89%)	343 (19,12%)	859 (47,88%)
Sudeste	4 (100,00%)	516 (30,94%)	1.304 (78,18%)
Sul	3 (100,00%)	349 (29,30%)	996 (83,63%)
Centro-Oeste	4 (100,00%)	215 (46,04%)	314 (67,24%)

Source: SINIS, 2020

3.4 Solid Waste Management Map

The Solid Waste Management Map is a platform that gathers information that influences solid waste management. On the 3D map, one can navigate throughout the national territory, and get to know up close the reality of waste management: sorting, recycling, treatment and final disposal units, in addition to Public Consortia and waste flows. Knowledge of these structures is essential to get the National Solid Waste Policy and the new Sanitation Legal Framework off the ground.

Figure 1 - Solid Waste Management Map, SINIS, 2020

Source: SINIS, 2020

Table 3 - Solid Waste Management Map, SINIR 2020

Source: SINIR, 2019

Figure 2 – National Waste Information System in Brazil 2020, with support from the R* tool

Variáveis	Brasil	Central	Nordeste	Norte	Sudeste
População Total (Média)	195538135 (42610.18)	15713080 (40707.46)	48032198 (37119.16)	16064628 (48097.69)	86616850 (58288.59)
População Urbana (Média)	169255573 (36882.89)	14161650 (36688.21)	36575743 (28265.64)	12463381 (37315.51)	80994607 (54505.12)
População Atendida (Média)	177039015 (38579)	14346167 (37166.24)	39895530 (30831.17)	12958273 (38797.22)	83198248 (55988.05)
Resíduos Coletados (Média)	62560965.2 (13632.81)	4936715.1 (12789.42)	16396283.8 (12671.01)	4780823.7 (14313.84)	28498599.8 (19178.06)
Variância População Total (Dp)	60104760570.39 (245162.72)	35007850439.33 (187103.85)	19644582601.04 (140159.13)	25494435280.5 (159669.77)	147190023871.29 (383653.52)
Variância População Urbana (Dp)	59151669881.48 (243211.16)	33257774179.84 (182367.14)	19294955591.9 (138906.28)	24728774010.81 (157253.85)	145253255931.64 (381121.05)
Variância População Atendida (Dp)	59063357252.32 (243029.54)	33704206743.09 (183587.05)	19084195611.25 (138145.56)	24456837113.02 (156386.82)	145040547932.74 (380841.89)
Variância Resíduos Coletados (Dp)	8200559480.15 (90556.94)	3151949554.02 (56142.23)	480763371.12 (69337.08)	3942879474.49 (62792.35)	18673695236.26 (136651.73)

Source: SINIR, 2019

Figure 3 - Normal Distribution

Source: Author

Figure 4 - Normal Distribution

Resíduos coletados Região Norte

Resíduos coletados Região Sudeste

Source: Author

Figure 5 - Normal Distribution

Resíduos coletados Região Sul

Source: Author

3.5 SNIS Indicators

This is a quantitative analysis of MSW waste (solid urban waste) collected in Brazil in 2020. Data were extracted in November 2022 on the SNIS website.

The descriptive and graphic analysis was developed in the Rstudio software. The database contained information collected from 4589 Brazilian municipalities. To perform the calculations, the MSW collection indicators divided by the population served were used. We performed the graphical analysis and Shapiro Test to test data normalities.

3.5.1 Results

Table 4 shows the distribution of MSW collection data by region in Brazil. The Southeast and Northeast regions were the ones that registered the most collections, representing 33% and 28%, respectively, of the studied sample. The sample has an average of 1017 tons of mass of MSW collected in relation to the per capita population, and a variation of 0.371 from the average.

Table 4 - Distribution table of mass collected from MSW per capita in 2020

	f	fr
Central	386	0.08
Nordeste	1294	0.28
Norte	334	0.07
Sudeste	1486	0.33
Sul	1089	0.24
TOTAL	4589	1
Média		1.017
Variância		0.371
Desvio Padrão		0.609

To test the normality of the data, we performed the Shapiro Test ($W = 0.89168$, $p\text{-value} < 2.2e-16$) and the graphical analysis of the histogram and QQ Plot, thus it is clear that the data do not have a normal distribution. Many factors can explain this difference in distribution, but we will analyze the graphs of regions first. Comparing the amount of mass collected and the

expenditure spent on collection in the Central region, we see a similarity in the curves, despite the density of expenditure being relatively lower than that of collection. In the South region, the movement of the curves shows that all investment in collection was proportionally reversed in the collection of this waste. On the other hand, we see a greater graphic area in expenses with collection in the Southeast region, when compared to what is collected, while in the Northeast we see the opposite.

Figure 6 – Collection X Expense Regions of Brazil

Source: SNIS 2020

The North region presented a MSW collection lower than the expenses, however, as it is a very industrial area, this graph may represent the division of expenses with the collection of other residues.

Figure 7 – Collection X Expense Regions of Brazil

Source: SNIS 2020

4 Results and Literature Discussion

Currently, the total annual generation of solid waste worldwide is approximately 17 billion tons and is expected to reach 27 billion by 2050 (Karak et al, 2012).

Currently, waste generated by maritime activities has been a source of much attention and concern, due to its potential to pollute. Pollution by plastic materials in the oceans, called microplastics, is a ubiquitous marine environmental problem.

Solid waste management is known to be a major contributor to many different environmental problems such as ecosystem damage and resource depletion due to inefficient recycling systems. The frightening increase in solid waste generation requires, therefore, management systems (Lazarevic et al, 2012).

QUANTITATIVE Analyzes for State Contribution to Waste Management.

(TITLE-ABS-KEY (“Integrated Management System”) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (“Waste Management”)) -61 Publications;

Figure 8 – Cloud of Terms in Relevance with Lines of Research

Source: Authors

Figure 9 – The 10 most relevant articles in Search

Nº	CITAÇÃO	TÍTULO	AUTOR	FONTE	QUALIS
1	79	Um sistema de gestão de pneus em fim de vida: Um estudo de caso português	Ferrão et al, 2008	Gestão de Resíduos	A1
2	44	Gestão de resíduos sólidos urbanos: Comparação energética e ambiental entre diferentes opções de gestão	Beccali et al, 2001	Jornal Internacional de Avaliação do Ciclo de Vida	A1
3	43	Os novos desafios dos sistemas de gestão de pneus em fim de vida: um estudo de caso espanhol	Uriburu et al, 013	Gestão de Resíduos	A1
4	33	Análise de incerteza na avaliação ambiental de um sistema integrado de gestão de resíduos de restauração e restauração em Espanha	Escobar et al, 2015	Jornal Internacional de Avaliação do Ciclo de Vida	A1
5	24	Sistemas integrados de gestão como um facilitador chave da gestão de riscos de segurança e saúde ocupacional: um estudo de caso em uma empresa de gerenciamento de resíduos de médio porte	Ramos et al, 2020	Jornal de Produção Mais Limpa	A1
6	24	Sistemas integrados de gestão como um facilitador chave da gestão de riscos de segurança e saúde ocupacional: um estudo de caso em uma empresa de gerenciamento de resíduos de médio porte	Ramos et al, 2020	Jornal de Produção Mais Limpa	A1
7	13	Repensando a sustentabilidade: uma revisão dos sistemas, status e desafios de gerenciamento de resíduos sólidos municipais da Libéria	David et al, 2020	Jornal de Ciclos de Materiais e Gestão de Resíduos	A2
8	04	IMSP: Sistema integrado de gestão de outorga de lançamento de poluentes hídricos baseado em um modelo híbrido C/S e B/S	Bi et al, 20110	Modelagem Ambiental e Software	A1
9	02	Investigando a geração e gestão de resíduos sólidos municipais em Ilorin para um possível sistema integrado de gestão de resíduos	Ibikunle et al, 2021	Jornal de Ciclos de Materiais e Gestão de Resíduo	A2
10	1	Manutenção de um sistema de gestão ambiental baseado na ISO 14001 em uma universidade privada brasileira, visando o desenvolvimento sustentável	Gomes et al, 2022	Jornal Internacional de Sustentabilidade no Ensino Superior	A1

Source: Scopus

The Integrated Management System (SGI) contributes managerially to improving performance on issues of the Environment, Quality, Health, Occupational Safety, Social Responsibility, being fundamental for organizations, workers and society as a whole (Mareth, 2015). The Integrated Management System is recommended in order to unify the processes of quality, safety, environmental management, occupational health and social responsibility, sustainable management practices and models of competences adopted by organizations, in order to result in beneficial procedures for society, economy and the environment (Munck, 2012). Implementing sustainable integrated management systems is a commitment towards developing the principles of Organizational Sustainability and guaranteeing the quality of its products and services, ensuring the preservation of the environment and risk-based thinking, according to (Barbosa, 2018) developing the culture organizational is one of the most critical factors for the proper development of standardized management systems and their integration and interaction with the business strategy, therefore, the development of an SGI must be led by senior management, in order to guarantee commitment to the process and organization's strategy.

According to the scientific literature Barbosa, (2019), reports that many companies are not aware of the difficulties in aligning the SGI with their strategy, thus, they do not see the market pressure to produce more with less resources and realize that the integration of all their management systems are vital to achieving sustainable and lasting benefits. Barbosa, also identified that the globalization of the economy and the recent financial crises lead organizations to live with new challenges, characterized by intense competitiveness and the current turbulent world competitive scenario, which demands the continuous modernization of the organizations' management instruments in a way that they stand out positively against the competition. (Simon et al., 2014) also reports that, in order to increase the chances of survival in this scenario and meet these demands, organizations have sought opportunities for operational, technological, and managerial improvements, which allow them, in an equitable way, to evolve from a productive, environmental and social point of view

The idealization of sustainable management means rethinking the basic concepts of SGI. Loizia et al., 2021 states that economic development incorporates several variables directly affected by specific technical aspects, considered in the assessment of sustainability with alternative solutions to the goals established by the circular economy and the European Green Pact (EGD). Karak et al, 2012 states that companies are increasingly concerned about the implementation of an integrated management system and environmental conservation. Currently, the total annual generation of solid waste worldwide is approximately 17 billion tons

and is expected to reach 27 billion by 2050 and in recent years, the global environmental concern has been to reinforce, discussions and propositions of goals in several countries to reduce pollutants released into the environment. Dias and Júnior, 2016, point out that environmental preservation is a frequent theme in the current business scenario where companies and governments are increasingly aware of the importance of conserving natural resources.

Abu Hajar et al. , 2020 reports that the growing increase in waste disposal in the environment is related to the disorderly growth of the population and per capita income, related to the inadequate production and consumption process, leading to the deterioration of the natural environment. Lazarevic et al (2012), recognizes solid waste management to be an important contributor to many different environmental problems, such as ecosystem damage and resource depletion, due to inefficient recycling systems and the frightening increase in solid waste generation, therefore , recommends management systems integrated with sustainable issues. In the conception of (Zorpas, 2020; Loizia et al, 2021a ; Voukali et al., 2021) the waste strategy is defined as a challenging process, which affects both the value chain and economic development and incorporates several variables directly affected by specific technical aspects, which must be considered when assessing the sustainability of alternative solutions, while simultaneously considering the goals established by the Circular Economy and the European Green Pact (EGD). (Ferronato and Torreta, 2019 , Li, 2019) analyzes that in recent years, this topic has aroused the interest of academia and based on the literature, mixed pollutants in the marine environment have their effects on aquatic life and human health and the basic laws for marine pollution control and regulation is still not accredited in many countries, resulting in an increase in the level of pollutants in marine systems is the biggest contributor, with serious effects, not only in obstructing certain natural aquatic processes, but also contributing to DNA damage and hindering important signaling pathways, as well as interference with the intestinal microbiota, leading to immunosuppression in marine fauna. (Li et al., 2016 ; Sun et al., 2021 ; Montero et al., 2022). Other systematic reviews have been performed. In recent times, the literature cites PM (microplastic) as the most researched plastic waste size category, with a size range of up to 5 mm, while tiny NP (nanoplastic) has a size range of 25 nm to 1 mm. The PM (microplastic) is determined by the nature of the polymer used in it, where the type of polymer decides the ecological impacts created in the ocean. a handful of studies have reported the physical and chemical properties of the polymers that make up PMs (Lambert et al., 2017, Andrady, 2017, Guo and Wang, 2019).

Currently, the waste generated by maritime activities has been a source of much attention and concern, due to its potential to pollute. By definition, (Cheshire et al, 2009), marine litter is considered to be any type of solid waste produced by man, generated on land or at sea that, intentionally or not, has been introduced into the marine environment, including the transport of these materials through from rivers, drainage, sewage systems or wind. Pollution by plastic materials in the oceans, called microplastics, is a ubiquitous marine environmental problem. Among industrial activities, exploration, drilling and production of oil in offshore fields, the first negative cause is the environmental impact, whether due to the volume of waste generated, their toxicity and the very specificity of the activity that takes place at high altitudes. -sea, where any lack of control could cause catastrophic impacts on the environment. Govindan, et al, 2014 explores Supply Chain (SC) practices to suggest the link between various entities, from the customer to the supplier, through manufacturing and services, so that the flow of materials, money and information can be effectively managed to meet business requirements. Azevedo et al. (2012a) consider that green and lean practices are two important pillars of sustainable business development. In the view of Schaltegger and Burritt (2017), regarding green practice, ISO 14001 certification impacts environmental and economic sustainability. For (Turrisi et al., 2013) the recovery and reuse of products contribute to reducing the negative effects on the environment, mainly by reducing waste disposal, extraction of raw materials and emissions from transport and distribution. In the literature, there is evidence of impacts on environmental and economic sustainability and Beullens (2004) states that the impact of “reverse logistics” on environmental sustainability can be found and reports that a green practice avoids waste, conserves natural resources such as energy and materials.

Prata et al, (2019) consider minimizing the input of plastic waste by reducing the source and waste management as one of the most valuable solutions to restore the oceans and using an integrated waste management system, focused on the hierarchy of the four R's (reduce, reuse, recycle, recover), improve the lifecycle of plastics to reduce energy and resource consumption, prevent harmful emissions, and decrease the amounts of mismanaged plastic waste that ends up in the oceans. The aim of this review was to discuss current strategies to improve the sustainability of plastics throughout their life cycle, including waste management, providing stakeholders with practical advice. Walker et al., (2016) propose cleanup activities as mitigation strategies, awareness raising tools and citizen science. However, removing all plastics from the environment seems impossible due to widespread environmental pollution with plastic particles of all sizes (Brennholt, 2018). Several authors in the literature agree that reducing the input of plastic waste through source reduction and waste management is one of the most valuable

solutions for restoring the oceans (Jambeck, et al, 2015; Brennholt, et al, 2018; Löhr, et al, 2017; Vince et al, 2017 and Al-Salem et al, 2009).

In the literature, sustainability-oriented innovation includes renewable resources, reverse logistics (RL), eco-efficiency, green supply chain and the involvement of the entire supply chain. It can also be considered an eco-friendly business strategy (Hansen et a, 2009 ; Katsikeas et al, 2016). In the current era of technological advancement, products with ecologically correct characteristics are rapidly emerging, but plastic waste poses challenges for societies, regardless of this advance (Huysman et al., 2017). Pohlen and Farris (1992) define reverse logistics as the flow of products from a consumer to a manufacturer in the distribution channel. The design of (LR) seeks to meet the needs of society, where natural resources are transformed into industrialized products when discarded and reach the end of their useful life. (de Oliveira et al, 2020) concludes that through it, it is understood that the reverse cycle starts from waste from the production process or customer consumption, and can go to disposal or return to the product cycle. One of the existing gaps in the literature on reverse logistics is discussed from the perspective of the consumer being scarce. In reverse logistics literature, consumers are not considered. There is a scarcity of literature on reverse logistics that considers the consumer as a source of waste return (Dixit and Badgaiyan).

In Santa Ana's view, by 2021 reverse logistics integrated with business logistics, the return of goods used by consumers to the business cycle, both after-sales and post-consumption, with the aim of adding value to the product, within economic, ecological, legal, logistical, or even with regard to corporate image. There is a distinction between Green Logistics and Reverse Logistics, since the first refers to the understanding and minimization of the ecological impact arising from logistics, that is, reduction in the use of materials, mode of transport, reuse of manufactured products, and the second, it moves reused materials that return to the traditional process of supply, production and distribution. Shi, Yuan et al., (2020) notes that “Reverse Logistics” has gone through several definitions over time, which have been adapting to the understanding of researchers. According to Sellito et al, (2013), RL is an adequate strategy to support the sustainable management of solid waste. In the work Green Logistics - Socio-Environmental Approach, DONATO (2008) defines Green Logistics or Ecologistics as “the part of logistics that is concerned with the environmental aspects and impacts caused by the logistics activity, which can bring environmental gains, as it has the purpose of sustainable development”.

5 Final Considerations

The SNIS is an important database platform with consolidated routines for the collection, administration, analysis, treatment, storage, organization and availability of information and indexes related to water and sanitation services in the municipalities of Brazil and the SNIR, National Information System on Solid Waste Management, instituted by the National Solid Waste Policy, which is an information system that collects, systematizes and integrates data related to solid waste management in Brazil.

In addition, SINIS seeks to synthesize the provision of basic sanitation services, making it possible to identify the main aspects for which it is necessary to define goals and measures capable of improving the scenario of basic sanitation in Brazil.

Over time, the historical series of data, SINIR, still does not completely minimize distortions in improving the quality of information and indices, as there are conflicts with other information systems.

Therefore, considering new evidence on the multiple risks that plastics pose to the environment, in 2015, the G7 Science Ministers meeting recognized the global risks posed by plastics to marine and coastal life, ecosystems and potentially the human health, compromising a priority Action Plan to combat Marine Litter through innovation, education, research and extension programs and the 2030 agenda that portrays the marine environment as suffering a large load of pollutants of the most varied types, where the vast amount of plastics and the activity of oil tankers and pipelines strongly contribute to water contamination.

6 REFERENCES

Abu Hajar, HA, Tweissi, A., Abu Hajar, YA, Al-Weshah, R., et al., 2020. **Assessment of the municipal solid waste management sector development in Jordan towards green growth by sustainability window analysis.** *J. Clean. Product* 258 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120539>.

Al-Salem, SM; Lettieri, P.; Baeyens, J. **Recycling and recovery routes of plastic solid waste (PSW): A review.** *Waste Management.* 2009, 29, 2625–2643.

Azevedo, Susana G., Helena Carvalho, and Virgilio Cruz-Machado. “ **A proposal of LARG supply chain management practices and a performance measurement system.** “ *International Journal of e-Education, e-Business, e-Management and e-Learning* 1.1 (2011): 7.

Barbosa, Luís César FM, Otívio Josí de Oliveira, and Gilberto Santos. “**Proposition for the alignment of the integrated management system (quality, environmental and safety) with the business strategy**.” *International Journal for Quality Research* 12.4 (2018): 925.

Barbosa, Luís César Ferreira Motta Barbosa. “**Guidelines for aligning the integrated management system with the strategy of industrial companies.**” (2019).

BIJOS, Júlia CBF et al. **Improving circularity in municipal solid waste management through machine learning in Latin America and the Caribbean.** *Sustainable Chemistry and Pharmacy*, v. 28, p. 100740, 2022.

BRAZIL. (2008) pbh/ecp>. Accessed on: 10 Oct. 2016. BRAZIL. (2008) **National Plan on Climate Change** . Brazil: Ministry of the Environment. 172 p. Available in: . Accessed on: 10 Aug. 2016.

_____. (2010a) Law nº 12.305, of August 2, 2010. Establishes the National **Solid Waste Policy; amends Law No. 9,605, of February 12, 1998;** and takes other measures. *Official Gazette of the Union, Brasilia*, section 1. 3 p.

_____. (2010c) Ministry of the Environment. **Manual for implementing composting and selective collection within public consortia.** Brazil: Ministry of the Environment/Secretary of Water Resources e. Urban Environment. 75 p.

Beullens, Patrick. “**Reverse logistics in effective recovery of products from waste materials.**” *Reviews in Environmental Science and Bio/Technology* 3.4 (2004): 283-306.

Brennholt, N.; Heß, M.; Reifferscheid, G. *Freshwater Microplastics*; **Springer International Publishing**: Cham, Switzerland, 2018; pp. 239–272.

Cheshire, Anthony, and Ellik Adler. “**UNEP/IOC guidelines on survey and monitoring of marine litter.**” (2009).

De Oliveira, Elaine Ferreira, et al. “**Reverse logistics: economic, social and environmental importance.**” *Brazilian Journal of Animal and Environmental Research* 3.4 (2020): 4325-4337.

Dixit, Saumya, and Anant Jyoti Badgaiyan. “**Towards improved understanding of reverse logistics—Examining mediating role of return intention.**” *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 107 (2016): 115-128.

DONATO, Vitorio, and Logística Verde. “**A socio-environmental approach.**” Rio de Janeiro, Editora Ciência Moderna (2008).

EIGENHEER, EM; FERREIRA, JA; ADLER, RR **Recycling: myth and reality.** Rio de Janeiro: Folio, 2005.

Jambeck, JR; Geyer, R.; Wilcox, C.; Siegler, TR; Perryman, M.; Andrady, A.; Narayan, R.; Law, KL **Plastic waste inputs from land into the ocean.** *Science* 2015, 347, 768–771.

Karak, T., Bhagat, RM, Bhattacharyya, P., 2012. **Municipal solid waste generation, composition, and management: the world scenario.** Crit. Rev. Environ. Sci. Technol. 42, 1509–1630.

Katsikeas, Constantine S., et al. “**Assessing performance outcomes in marketing.**” Journal of marketing 80.2 (2016): 1-20.

Govindan, K., Azevedo, SG, Carvalho, H., & Cruz-Machado, V. (2014). **Impact of supply chain management practices on sustainability.** Journal of Cleaner production, 85, 212-225.

Hansen, FK, et al. “**Power asymmetry in cosmic microwave background fluctuations from full sky to sub-degree scales: is the universe isotropic?.**” The Astrophysical Journal 704.2 (2009): 1448.

Huysman, Sofie, et al. “**Performance indicators for a circular economy: A case study on post-industrial plastic waste.**” Resources, conservation and recycling 120 (2017): 46-54.

Lazarevic, D., Buclet, N., Brandt, N., 2012. **The application of life cycle thinking in the context of European waste policy.** J. Clean. Product 29–30, 199–207.

LI, Wai Chin, HF Tse, and Lincoln Fok. “**Plastic waste in the marine environment: A review of sources, occurrence and effects.**” Science of the total environment 566 (2016): 333-349.

Li, Jiana, et al. “**Using mussel as a global bioindicator of coastal microplastic pollution.**” Environmental pollution 244 (2019): 522-533.

Lohr, A.; Savelli, H.; Beunen, R.; Kalz, M.; Ragas, A.; Belleghen, FV **Solutions for global marine litter pollution.** Curr. opinion Environ. Support 2017, 28, 90–99. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef][Green Version.

Loizia, Pantelitsa, et al. “**Measuring the level of environmental performance on coastal environment before and during the COVID-19 pandemic: a case study from Cyprus.**” Sustainability 13.5 (2021): 2485.

Mareth, Bruna Lira. “**Evaluation of the labeling of energy supplements based on carbohydrates marketed in Brasília.**” (2015).

Munck, L., BORIM-DE-SOUZA, R.; ZAGUI, C. **Management by Competencies and its relationship with actions aimed at Sustainability.** REGE, São Paulo – SP, Brazil, v. 19, no. 3, p. 377-394, Jul./Sept. 2012

Prata, Joana C., et al. “**Solutions and integrated strategies for the control and mitigation of plastic and microplastic pollution.**” International journal of environmental research and public health 16.13 (2019): 2411.

Pohlen, Terrance L., and M. Theodore Farris. “**Reverse logistics in plastics recycling.**” International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management (1992).

Santa Ana, Márcio de Freitas, et al. **“SUSTAINABILITY, PLANETARY LIMITS AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT.”** Ibero-American Journal of Humanities, Sciences and Education (2021): 11-50.

Shi, Yuan, et al. **“Cleaner alumina production from coal fly ash: Membrane electrolysis designed for sulfuric acid leachate.”** Journal of Cleaner Production 243 (2020): 118470.

Simon, Alexandra, et al. **“An empirical analysis of the integration of internal and external management system audits.”** Journal of Cleaner Production 66 (2014): 499-506.

Sellitto, Miguel Afonso, et al. **“Management of green supply chains: framework.”** Revista Produção Online 13.1 (2013): 351-374.

Schaltegger, Stefan, and Roger Burritt. **Contemporary environmental accounting: issues, concepts and practice.** Routledge, 2017.

Turrisi, Mario, Manfredi Bruccoleri, and Salvatore Cannella. **“ Impact of reverse logistics on supply chain performance.”** International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management (2013).

VALLINI, G. **Planning ahead: waste management as a cornerstone in a world with limited resources.** Waste Management & Research, 27: 623, 2009.

Vince, J.; Hardesty, BD **Plastic pollution challenges in marine and coastal environments: From local to global governance.** Restor. Eco. 2016, 25, 123–12.

Zorpas, AA; Pedreno, J. Navarro; Candel, BM Almendro. **Heavy metals overview in the framework of wastewater, sewage sludge, and soil treatment and removal.** The study-case of zeolite. Arabian Journal of Geoscience, v. 14, p. 1-19, 2021

Walker TR, Pettipas S., Bernier M., Xanthos D., Day A. **Canada's Dirty Dozen: A Canadian policy framework to mitigate plastic pollution.** [(accessed on 31 December 2016)];Zone Fall Coast. Zone Can. Assoc. Newsl. 2016:9–12.